

INDUSTRY 4.0 TECHNOLOGIES TO PROMOTE THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN AGRICULTURE

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Summary- With an estimated population of 9 billion in 2050, the challenges for agriculture are enormous, and factors such as reduction of inputs such as water and energy, nutrient conditions in the soil, and climatic factors are only sometimes favorable. Thus, implementing Industry 4.0 technologies in agriculture associated with Circular Economy practices presents opportunities for sustainable development with economic, environmental, and social benefits.

Keywords: Agriculture 4.0; Circular Economy; Economic sustainability; Environmental sustainability; social sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

The digital transformation in agriculture using Industry 4.0 technologies enables the development of agricultural scenarios with sensors collecting data on environmental characteristics, soil, water quantity, and plantation. Data is stored on cloud servers and analyzed with Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Neural Networks, and Big Data tools. This way, we transform large amounts of data into information, allowing farmers to make operational and strategic management decisions more assertively.

The adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies in agriculture has enormous potential to increase productivity, control the product life cycle and cooperation in the production chain [1], with historical data management [2], automation of production processes using Internet of Things technologies, Big Data and traceability in product transportation [3] and decision support systems [4].

With the use of drinking water in agriculture being scarce in some areas, its consumption must be controlled with irrigation control systems with IoT sensors [5], especially in places with little rainfall [6], and with environmental data collected from meteorological stations, controlling the water level in the soil to take advantage of evapotranspiration [7].

Agriculture 4.0 uses Industry 4.0 technologies that allow for improving the sustainability of crops, planting and harvesting [8], better working conditions [9], and waste reduction [10] with a reduction in the environmental footprint [11], conservation of soil [12], social gains resulting from meeting human demands [13] and management and decision-making systems [14].

Adopting technologies in Agriculture 4.0 and Circular Economy practices challenges with a lack of government support [15] and a lack of workers prepared to use new technologies [16].

DEVELOPMENT

The research proposal was to verify the technologies used in Industry 4.0 to promote the Circular Economy in Agriculture. For this purpose, a Bibliometric and Systematic Review of the literature to understand the agribusiness scenario illustrated in

Fig. 1 and which technologies used in Industry 4.0 are already in use.

Figure 1– Agribusiness chain

Fig. 2 shows the results of the most used technologies and the combination of some of them. We observed that IoT, Cloud, Big Data, and AI technologies have been adopted in innovative farm projects, providing economic and environmental development for agriculture.

Figure 2 – Radar of the frequency of use of Industry 4.0 technologies in Agriculture

Fig. 3 presents a radar of how Industry 4.0 technologies applied in Agriculture relate to the benefits generated, with the first concern being environmental and social development, which still needs little to be adopted.

Figure 2 – Radar with a list of articles focusing on Environmental, Economic, Social, and Circular Economy in Agriculture 4.0

The next step was the analysis of the tools proposed by the ReSOLVE framework [17] and how they could be inserted into Smart Agriculture or Agriculture 4.0, contributing to environmental, economic, and social benefits and the use of Circular Economy.

Fig. 4 presents the ReSOLVE framework used to understand and adopt Industry 4.0 technologies that can be applied in Agriculture and thus build scenarios that generate economic, environmental, and social benefits and the development of farms and the entire Agribusiness production chain.

Figure 3—Ellen MacArthur Foundation ReSOLVE Framework [17]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Experts in agronomy, farmers, cloud provider managers, and experts in Big Data and AI positively evaluated the proposal to use Industry 4.0 technologies to promote the Circular Economy in Agriculture.

We can then adopt Industry 4.0 technologies on farms so that access to technological innovations is not restricted to large producers but to medium and small producers, providing a more collaborative, productive ecosystem.

Circular Economy strategies associated with adopting Industry 4.0 technologies enable opportunities to generate new business and social sustainability.

The contributions of this research on Industry 4.0 technologies to promote the Circular Economy in Agriculture involve the expansion of theoretical knowledge of the application of the Circular Economy in Agriculture, opportunities to develop sustainable practices with new technologies, and the possibility of generating new jobs and income.

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